

METHODOLOGICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR ORGANIZING OPEN CLASSES IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *In this article, open classes conducted by medical educational institutions in all directions, requirements for their implementation, plan, methodology, guidelines for conducting open classes, and the importance of ensuring the quality of education rni and its importance are highlighted. Information about the possibilities, disadvantages and advantages of conducting open classes in the educational system is presented..*

Key words: *Interactive methods, regulatory documents, quality of education, mastering indicators, mastering efficiency.*

INTRODUCTION.

In accordance with the requirements of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” and the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated February 16, 2006 No. 25 “On the further improvement of the system of retraining of pedagogical personnel and their professional development”, the Regulation was developed, and regardless of the provisions of this regulation, all academic lyceums and professions-determining the procedure for organizing and holding open training sessions in vocational colleges.

Experienced pedagogues, scientists and specialists in this field of knowledge are invited to the open training session. It is recommended that young pedagogues attend open training sessions.

Open educational sessions serve as an experimental field for introducing modern pedagogical and information technologies, interactive teaching methods into the educational process, and a school of pedagogical skills for young pedagogues.

Open educational sessions must be conducted by experienced teachers of the educational institution once every 2 years.

The main purpose of open training sessions:

- a) improving the professional skills of teachers;
- b) training young pedagogues to teach using advanced pedagogical technologies and interactive teaching methods;
- c) Continuous development of professional and pedagogical skills based on the requirements of state educational standards (State requirements);
- g) is to regularly update the professional knowledge, qualifications and skills of teachers.

The main part. Open educational sessions are held in subjects provided for in professional education curricula, including general professional and specialty subjects.

The plan of open training sessions is drawn up with the participation of teachers in relevant departments (departments) and, after discussion and approval, is approved by the deputy director of educational affairs of the educational institution.

Open training sessions are usually designed for two academic hours.

The topic of open training sessions is chosen by the teacher according to the calendar subject plan.

Open educational activities should be a factor for students' education, intellectual development, becoming a well-rounded person, and physical and mental stability. Open educational sessions should be directed to students' activity, independent thinking, mastery of the subject, and creative research. In the training scenario, it is necessary to take into account that the scientific basis of the lesson (practical training, laboratory work, etc.), the accuracy of the covered topic, the place of the development of modern science, as well as the integrity of the connection between the disciplines, the existence of problem situations should ensure that the students receive thorough knowledge. according to Advanced pedagogical technologies and interactive teaching methods should be used in open educational sessions.

The teacher should pay special attention to the following in the process of preparing for the open educational session:

- a) optimal planning of training time;
- b) in-depth study of the sources selected for use;
- v) taking into account the capabilities of students in the academic group (determining the skill level of previously acquired knowledge to explain the topic);
- g) depending on the type of training, choosing its style and tools correctly;
- d) To provide students with in-depth knowledge based on the requirements of state educational standards.

When choosing the subject of an open educational session, the teacher's pedagogical and professional skills, teaching methodology, knowledge and teaching tools should be clearly reflected. In the period of preparation for the open educational session, the teacher should make extensive use of scientific and methodological research, demonstrative and didactic materials, technical means of teaching, and information and communication technologies. Also, it is necessary to plan in advance the sequence of use of demonstrative and demonstrated weapons. The activities of the teacher and students (what they should be doing) during the specified time should be clearly defined in the scenario. The members of the department (department) should provide the teacher with scientific-methodical, technical, material and analytical support in the process of preparation for the open training session.

The methodological complex of the open educational session consists of the following: a) calendar subject plan of the subject;

- b) lecture text (basic synopsis) or lesson plan (laboratory work, practice, independent work, course project, etc.);
- c) the scenario of an open training session;
- g) didactic, demonstration materials, information communication and technical tools indicated in the scenario;
- d) a set of questions for control work (reinforcement of the lesson);
- e) a set of questions or problems for homework.

The composition of the methodological complex is selected in connection with the type of training (lesson).

The purpose of open training can be defined as follows: a) use of computer equipment in practical training;

- b) the role of problem teaching in the educational process;
- c) integrity of interdisciplinarity;
- g) ensuring independent work of students;
- d) acceleration of students' learning process;

e) increase the effectiveness of students' use of existing didactic materials, methodical guides and equipment in training.

An announcement will be made to the participants of the academic lyceum (vocational college) about the open training session one week in advance. In the announcement, the topic of the open educational session, the teacher's name and surname, academic degree, title, category, as well as the place, day, time and number of the academic group are indicated.

Teachers of nearby educational institutions, specialists of production enterprises, professors-teachers of related departments of higher educational institutions attached to the academic lyceum (vocational college) can be invited to the open training session.

Discussion of the results of open training sessions A detailed discussion on the content and scientific-methodical level of the open training sessions is held in the relevant science department (department) during free time and formalized with a report. External feedback on the open educational session is submitted in writing to the management of the secondary special vocational education institution. When evaluating the results of the open training session, the opinions of the experts of the higher educational institution and production enterprises attached to the educational institution are considered a priority. In the discussion, the speakers should fully reveal the achievements and shortcomings of the Open Training, and give recommendations for eliminating the identified shortcomings. The discussion should be organized in an open, objective and friendly atmosphere.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS.

Materials from high-quality open training sessions should be recommended for dissemination among teachers. The results of open training sessions organized by them at a high level are taken into account in the material and moral stimulation of medical pedagogues and professors, as well as in recommending them for State awards. The results of open training sessions are an important factor in determining the annual rating indicators of teachers, popularizing their experience, certification process, and raising qualification categories.

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